

Assessing Accessibility of Health Care for the Oldest Old

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Abstract

This paper analyzes health care accessibility for the oldest old. The empirical basis for this work is data obtained through a qualitative sociological survey of individuals aged 85 and over. It has been shown that the current situation regarding access to medical care for this age group is extremely challenging. The most significant barriers are physical ones, caused by their physical and cognitive limitations, as well as specifics of health care organization within the national healthcare system. Additionally, sociocultural barriers limit health care accessibility for the oldest old. Discrimination against older adults, for example ageism among health care providers is common. The identified limitations and barriers reduce the accessibility of medical consultations and medications. The most vulnerable to limited access to health care are older adults with limited mobility, bedridden, and those with significant cognitive impairments.

Effective measures to improve accessibility of health care for the oldest old require reliable data, reflecting the needs and problems of this age group. The study shows that standard sociological tools are extremely limited in their ability to survey the oldest old due to their physical and cognitive health. To obtain adequate data, sociological tools must be adjusted with due regard to the characteristics, specific to this age group, and specialized surveys must be conducted.

Keywords

oldest old, qualitative interviews, accessibility and quality of medical services, medication accessibility, surveys

JEL codes: I14, I18, J14, C81

Introduction

Population ageing is a current global demographic trend. The share of older people in the population is steadily increasing. This includes a growing proportion of people aged 85 and over, also known as the oldest old. According to UN estimates, the share of the oldest old in the world population equaled to 0.9% in 2023. By 2050, this figure could rise to 2.2%¹, while in high-income countries, this figure could reach 4.1% (United Nations 2024).

Human ageing invariably involves a decline in physical and cognitive functions, an increase in chronic morbidity, and the onset of age-specific diseases. Deteriorating health, particularly in the oldest age groups, increases the demand for healthcare services (Ageing and Health 2016). Access to medical services is critical to the well-being of the oldest old. A key factor in developing effective policies to improve access to healthcare for older adults is the availability of relevant and reliable empirical data on their needs.

Microdata from large-scale sociological surveys are the most important source of information on population health and health care accessibility. However, surveying older adults, especially the oldest age groups, is associated with significant challenges. Specific health conditions of older adults (in particular, various physical and cognitive limitations) can make it difficult to reach respondents. Additionally, standard questionnaires may be too complex for older adults. Hearing and vision impairments, as well as cognitive disorders, often prevent older adults from providing adequate answers. General weakness, which is often characteristic of older adults, can also significantly limit the time available for interviews, resulting in incomplete interviews. Functional impairments can influence subjective assessments, especially those related to health and needs for medical services.

Thus, the oldest old may be underrepresented in the national survey data. Additionally, the sample may be significantly biased towards healthier individuals, who can participate in surveys and provide information. There are also limitations to the completeness and reliability of data, especially when a standard questionnaire is used for the survey (Lundberg and Thorslund 1996; Hardy et al. 2009; Kelfve et al. 2013). To better understand the socio-economic and health statuses and health care needs of older adults, several countries (e.g., Sweden² and Japan³) conduct specialized surveys.

In Russia, issues regarding the assessment of health factors and accessibility of medical services for the oldest age groups of the elderly are quite acute. According to Rosstat data, as of January 1, 2023, 2.1 million people in Russia (1.4% of the total population) were aged 85+ (Demographic Yearbook 2023). However, the amount of specialized data on the oldest old available to researchers is currently limited. These individuals are not the focus of relevant scientific research due to lack of adequate and complete information. This study qualitatively investigates the accessibility of health care for people aged 85+ in one region of the Russian Federation. The study results make it possible to qualitatively identify major practices and barriers to accessing health care for this age group. Additionally, the survey enables us to draw conclusions about the feasibility of applying standard methodological approaches to surveys of the oldest old.

1 According to the medium variant of the demographic forecast.

2 For further detail see Swedish panel study of living conditions of the oldest old 2011. URL: <https://snd.se/en/catalogue/dataset/ext0010-4>.

3 For further detail see The Tokyo Oldest Old Survey on Total Health. URL: <https://www.keio-centenarian.com/english/tooth>.

The article is structured as follows: the second section provides an overview of the existing literature on the analysis of barriers to accessing medical services for older adults. The third section describes the survey methodology and approaches to processing the obtained information. The fourth section uses the survey data to discuss characteristics and barriers to accessing medical services and medications for the oldest old. Section five discusses peculiarities of applying standard approaches to surveys of the oldest old. The final, sixth section presents major conclusions of the study.

Review of studies on access to health care for older adults

The accessibility of healthcare services for older citizens in different countries is a widely discussed topic in scientific literature. In our review, we will focus on studies examining this issue in developed countries.

The literature currently highlights the following five domains of health care accessibility: approachability; acceptability, availability and accommodation, affordability and appropriateness (Levesque et al. 2013). Affordability is defined as a patient ability to pay for the necessary medical services. Barriers to affordability for older citizens are significant in all countries, including those with high levels of health insurance coverage, such as European countries (European Commission 2008; Palm et al. 2021). This is largely due to the fact that the growing demand for health care among the elderly often leads to higher out-of-pocket payments, i.e. medical expenses not covered by insurance. Given low incomes of older adults, this situation can result in higher unmet demand for health care in this age group, particularly among the oldest age groups. At the national level, affordability of healthcare for older adults depends on the principles of the healthcare system and the income level of this age group (Sowa-Kofta et al. 2021; Iecovich and Carmel 2009; Schoen et al. 2005).

In addition to economic barriers, limited physical access to health care poses a significant challenge to older adults seeking healthcare. Moreover, in developed countries, these barriers are often the leading cause of unmet demand for health care among older adults. Various physical and cognitive limitations can significantly restrict the ability of older adults to reach health care facilities and wait for appointments. Physical accessibility of care for older adults is also reduced due to limited transportation options, as well as a lack of facilities and equipment in medical buildings to accommodate people with special needs (European Commission 2008; Fitzpatrick et al. 2004; Nemet and Bailey 2000; Gaans and Dent 2018). Physical accessibility of health care varies depending on the type of care. Older adults experience the least difficulty accessing primary care, whereas specialized care is much more difficult to access (European Commission 2008; Iecovich, Carmel 2009; Suominen-Taipale et al. 2004). Barriers to physical accessibility are most pronounced in the oldest age groups (European Commission 2008; Iecovich and Carmel 2009) and among those with more severe functional limitations (European Commission 2008; Chaix et al. 2005). The situation is particularly challenging for bedridden older adults living at home (Herr et al. 2014).

A specific sociocultural barrier to health care for older adults is ageism, or age discrimination by health care providers. According to literature, compared to younger people, older people are more likely to receive cheaper treatment. Advanced, high-tech treatment methods are less likely to be used for the elderly. They are also less likely to undergo regular checkups and participate in rehabilitation programs. Doctors and nurses sometimes dismiss the needs of older adults. Healthcare workers are less attentive, respectful, and patient with

the elderly. Oldest age groups are relatively more likely to encounter ageism (Ayalon and Tesch-Römer 2018).

The accessibility of drug therapy for older adults is an essential component of modern health care that largely determines health status and needs to be discussed separately. One key problem is drug prescription without considering the patient age, other diseases, and other drugs being used (Viktil et al. 2007; Barry and Hughes 2021). Other problems with drug therapy for the elderly include difficulties in monitoring health of patients on therapy due to both specifics of medical practice and limitations in accessibility of medical consultations (Syed et al. 2013). Additionally, a common issue in drug therapy for the elderly is non-compliance with the prescribed medication regimens (Col et al. 1990). Only 26%-59% of the elderly patients adhere to their prescribed medication regimen (Eijken et al. 2003). The older the patient, the higher the likelihood of noncompliance. The oldest old often cannot manage their medication therapy independently and require assistance (Yap et al. 2016).

Relatively little research has been devoted to analyzing characteristics and factors affecting accessibility of health care for older people, especially the oldest old. Overall, the results of such research demonstrate significant limitations in health care accessibility for older adults. Despite differences in health systems, older people experience similar problems when seeking health care as their peers abroad. Notably, there are significant physical barriers related to both patient health limitations and lack of specialized doctors in polyclinics. These barriers are especially pronounced for older adults with significant mobility limitations, senile asthenia, and multiple chronic diseases (Gruzdeva and Barsukov 2018; Mukharyamova and Savelyeva 2019; Trofimova et al. 2021; Shigabutdinov 2012).

Older people also often encounter ageism among healthcare workers. Patient complaints are ignored, examinations are insufficient, and poor health in older patients is considered a normal part of aging by healthcare workers. (Gruzdeva and Barsukov 2018; Trofimova et al. 2021). Russian seniors relatively rarely face economic barriers to receiving medical consultations; however, the issue of medication affordability is very pressing. Lack of drug insurance coupled with low retirement incomes often means that older people cannot afford modern medications (Novokreschenova and Senchenko 2014; Mukharyamova and Savelyeva 2019).

This paper contributes to the research on health care accessibility for the most vulnerable elderly population: the oldest old. Based on qualitative research conducted by the authors, this paper analyzes practices for receiving health care and identifies major barriers to care accessibility for this group. The analysis of medication accessibility is a distinct focus of this study. Another important objective of the paper is to evaluate the feasibility of using standard approaches to survey oldest age groups.

Research methodology

During the study, twelve qualitative interviews with the oldest old aged 85+ were conducted. The interviews took place in three cities in the Republic of Khakassia: Abakan, Abaza, and Chernogorsk⁴. Seven of the twelve respondents were able to independently provide infor-

⁴ The Republic of Khakassia is located in the southwestern part of Eastern Siberia and is part of the Siberian Federal District. According to Rosstat data, the population of the Republic of Khakassia in 2022 was estimated at 530.000 people (71st place out of 85 Russian regions). In 2022, GRP per capita in the Republic equaled to 657.000 rubles (44th place), life expectancy added up to 70.6 years (63rd place), and the share of the population aged 85 and over equaled to 0.97% (64th place).

mation about themselves. However, due to health limitations, five respondents failed to fully participate in the interview. In such cases, caregivers (relatives) were actively involved in the interview.

Based on relevant literature review, the interview scenario included sections on the respondent health, health care delivery, and drug provision. Additionally, the interviews identified major sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents and their households. The respondents were recruited with the support of the regional Ministry of Labor and Social Protection.

Audio recordings of the interviews were transcribed using an artificial intelligence system (ChatGPT) and then reviewed. These transcripts were then used to generate text fragments for the analyst's retelling. This process provided additional anonymization of the interviews while preserving the meaning, emotional tone, and speech characteristics of the respondent narratives. A more detailed description of the research methodology is presented in (Rogozin 2024).

Results

Accessibility of medical services

The oldest old experience significant health deterioration. All interview participants live with some degree of ill health and have somehow adapted to constant discomfort, pain, and physical and cognitive limitations. They believe that their condition is normal for their age and cannot be improved.

A woman aged 88, Abakan

“My health is very poor. I am 88 years old. My joints hurt, and I have difficulty walking. I can only walk with canes. When I was 85, I was still active, working at my dacha and then my health got rapidly worse, just like that. Nothing really happened, but my health has been just deteriorating. There is no one to treat me. Hospitals won't admit me [...] They said, they didn't usually perform surgery at my age. All there is to do is to bear it.”

A daughter of a 97-year-old woman, Abaza

“Everything was fine until she turned 96. And then, suddenly, it all changed. Her blood pressure is quite high. I think she might have had a microstroke. A sudden memory loss and slurred speech. But that's just my opinion. There's no point in going to the doctor – they won't tell us anything anyway.”

A woman aged 92, Chernogorsk

“Medicine is not to blame. I am no longer capable and I haven't found anything medical related to how I feel. There are many things I can't manage on my own [...] No medicine can help with the old age.”

As the interview excerpts show, the oldest old have little hope that medical assistance or seeing a doctor will improve their condition. Moreover, medicine in general is perceived as something formal and hostile. It is something that must be sought, demanded or refused, and the oldest old must cope on their own. Conversations about medicine tend to focus on complaints and lamentations. This attitude is largely due to the limited accessibility of quality medical services for the oldest old. Barriers to physical accessibility of medical services come to the fore. Due to various illnesses, physical limitations, and general weakness, the oldest old are often unable to travel to a health care facility for treatment. The possibility to call a doctor for a home visit under the system of compulsory health insurance is also limited. While general practitioners still visit patients at home, it is difficult to arrange specialized doctor visits.

A woman aged 97, Abaza

[Interviewer]: “Why don’t you go to the hospital? Can’t you call to ask for a home visit?”

[Respondent]: “I used to go to the hospital until I got very sick. But when you’re sick, how can you get to the hospital? And you can’t call for a doctor [...] I’m so weak that I don’t want even to see anyone.”

A woman aged 85, Abaza

“I haven’t been able to get to the doctor’s office for a long time. It’s always a problem: getting dressed, finding transportation, a taxi or asking a neighbor for a ride. You have to wait, even if you have made an appointment beforehand, you have to wait in line again.”

People with limited mobility and bedridden face particular challenges in accessing medical services. The requirement of being physically present at the doctor’s office makes medical care practically inaccessible to them without a regular and active help of their relatives.

A daughter of an 87-year woman, Abakan

“Even for someone without legs, obtaining a disability status is very challenging. You would think they would certify you a disability group at the hospital where your legs were amputated, but they don’t. There are a lot of other things they don’t provide; they drag it out. It took a year to receive a disability group after my mother lost her legs [...] We hire people to carry her on a stretcher to the hospital because she has to be there in person. No specialist will come to our place unless you pay them.”

Health care facilities are often not adapted to accommodate patients with limited mobility, creating additional barriers to accessing medical services for the oldest old, who often have mobility limitations. Even involving relatives does not solve the issue.

A wife of an 88-year man, Chernogorsk

“He needs to be transported there somehow, you understand? The psychotherapist sees patients only in the other settlement. The hospital is in a four-story building without an elevator. And how is he going to sit and wait out there? He constantly needs to use the toilet; he won’t be able to hold it in.”

Physical limitations to medical services also include the lack of doctors with the necessary specialty in polyclinics and hospitals. The interviews were conducted in three settlements – a regional center, a medium-sized town, and a small town. However, the informants noted the shortage of doctors, especially narrow specialty, everywhere. The informants often perceive the lack of doctors as the norm due to low salaries in medicine.

A woman aged 89, Abaza

“The situation with doctors is even more complicated. For example, the head of the polyclinic goes out of town. And you have to wait. Two weeks pass. The urologist goes out of town, too. Wait again. Another two weeks pass [...] You can wait to see the district doctor⁵, but they are useless.”

A daughter-in-law of an 89-year man, Abakan:

“Things got so bad with the specialist doctors at the hospital that we had to become specialists ourselves. We became as good as we could get.”

A daughter of a 90-year-old woman, Chernogorsk:

“At least we now have a district doctor. There hasn’t been a district doctor out here for ten years. I’m so glad we have doctors at all. I would not expect any doctors to work for these salaries.”

5 District doctor – a physician in Russia who is assigned to a small area (district or neighborhood) who is supposed to be the primary care provider for the population of this area

In addition to limited physical accessibility, the oldest old face significant sociocultural barriers to medical services, associated with ageism. The oldest old often encounter dismissive attitudes on the part of medical professionals. Their complaints are being ignored, and doctors attribute their poor health to their old age. The informants complain that doctors are inattentive, spend little time with them, and do not explain things well.

A man aged 89, Abakan

“I have got many ailments [...] Doctors are in no hurry to help people like me. They only have one answer: ‘What do you expect with a state like that?’”

A man aged 89, Abakan

“The district doctor came once; I don’t even remember when. She didn’t even take off her coat or sit down. She stood next to me for a little while and left. That’s how they treat you these days.”

The inaccessibility of free medical services in state institutions forces the oldest old and their relatives to seek paid services. Feedback on paid services is generally positive. Doctors who are paid directly by their patients, tend to treat them more attentively, and the prescribed treatment brings relief.

A wife of an 82-year-old man, Abakan

“That’s why I hired a doctor. She comes to our house and charges 1.500 rubles. She helped my husband, she gave me injections as well, and talked to us like to human beings.”

It should be noted that none of the informants mentioned the cost of medical services being too high. However, not everyone uses paid medical services. Therefore, it is difficult to draw conclusions about affordability of medical services for the oldest old based on the survey data. Further research is needed.

Medication accessibility

The study results show that nearly all informants are entitled to free or subsidized drugs, mainly on the basis of having a Group I or Group II disability. Despite this, medication provision to the oldest old is very complicated. During the interviews, almost all informants mentioned that the free drugs they were entitled to were actually inaccessible. A high level of bureaucracy involved in obtaining “free” prescriptions, the need to visit a doctor in person, and the significant time commitment reduce accessibility of free drugs.

Obtaining or renewing a prescription for free medications requires a personal visit to a doctor. As discussed above, this is difficult for the oldest old due to health restrictions. Relatives who care for the oldest old could obtain prescriptions instead, but due to significant time costs, these relatives, who often combine caregiving with work, are unable to do so. Consequently, the oldest old are forced to purchase drugs at their own expense.

A woman aged 92, Abaza

“I used to receive subsidized drugs. Now, however, we don’t go anywhere; we don’t try to get it. The record says I only have to pay 50% for the medicine, but we pay the full amount [...] I’m old now. I can’t go anywhere. Where would I go? My legs fail me [...] My son doesn’t have time, and he’s not pushy enough to manage it. He won’t deal with this. We pay in full, and that’s it”.

A woman aged 85, Abaza

“I am entitled to free medication, but I have given up and no longer use the subsidy [...] While I could walk, I would get my medication for free, but now I don’t have any strength, all I can manage is to buy it.”

Another limitation to the accessibility of “free” medication is unavailability of “free” prescription drugs in pharmacies. Even if you manage to get a prescription, it is difficult to ob-

tain the medication. You have to search for the medication and visit several pharmacies or travel to another locality.

A man aged 91, Abakan

“It may not be difficult to get a prescription, but finding the medication is another matter. There is a social pharmacy nearby. You go there, but the medication is out of stock. You turn onto Lenin Street and hobble over there, but it’s not available there either. You go to the poly-clinic and ask the person in charge of medication. They don’t have it, but you can ask. They send you to Chernogorka. That’s where I found my medication.”

Another problem associated with the use of medication by the oldest old is ensuring adequate drug therapy and compliance with the regimen. Due to the limited accessibility of medical consultations, the oldest old are used to make their own decisions about which drugs to take, when to start and discontinue the therapy, as well as dosage adjustments. They often choose medications and dosages based on their experience or the advice of relatives, friends, or pharmacists.

A woman aged 85, Abaza

“I was hospitalized for diabetes. They treated me and gave me all kinds of prescriptions. I took them at first, but then I stopped.”

A woman aged 89, Abaza

“The doctor prescribes something, but I used to be a pharmacist, so I know how the cookie crumbles. You can’t fool me when it comes to medications, and you can’t hide your incompetence. I don’t take everything that is prescribed. I piece together everything, and then I know what I’m taking.”

A man aged 89, Abakan

“A girl I know at the pharmacy helps me a lot. She gives me medicines that relieve my pain well.”

Essentially, only the oldest old under constant care, with medication intake strictly monitored by caregivers, adhere to the prescribed treatment regimen. However, often neither the elderly nor their caregivers understand the relationship between health conditions and medications, or the purpose of treatment. Taking medication is often perceived as a ritualistic action performed only because it is required and prescribed by the doctor.

A woman aged 92, Abaza

“Our medication is very expensive. It’s for treating everything.”

A wife of an 82-year-old man, Abakan

“I give him medications to calm myself down. I feel calm when he takes pills. They prescribed Cardiomagnyl, Vinpocetine, and some vitamins one day. We take everything they told us to take, but I don’t know why or what good it does.”

Feasibility of using standard methods for surveying the oldest old

The survey scenario included standard questions to assess the informant on health and functional limitations⁶. In particular, the informants were asked to rate their health on a 100-point scale. Virtually none of the informants were able to provide a score. The oldest old

6 The interview format included questions from the European Quality of Life Questionnaire EQ-5D-3L (<https://spb.hse.ru/data/2020/03/10/1563014698/EQ-5D-3L.pdf>). The EQ-5D-3L tool is widely used in various countries, particularly for developing and monitoring effectiveness of health preservation and promotion policies.

complain about their health and describe their ailments in sufficient detail, but have difficulty rating their health on a scale.

On the one hand, they confuse meanings, cannot understand the task and comprehend the question. On the other hand, the question itself is irrelevant to their condition and well-being. Polymorbidity and living with pain prevent them from even thinking about health; assessing health seems inappropriate to them. They are alive, and that is enough.

A woman aged 89, Abaza

[Interviewer]: *[explaining the scale]* “One hundred is excellent, the best possible. Zero is pain; everything is over. Nothing is left. [Informant] Well, health... Well, when I... How am I? I don’t know. I can’t tell you now, what percentage of my health I have got right now. From zero to one hundred. Well, health, as they say, well, I can walk... That’s that. I walk.”

Reducing the number of intervals on the response scale does not lead to success. Even on a five-point scale, it is difficult for the oldest old to accurately assess their health.

A man aged 91, Abakan

[Interviewer]: “How would you rate your health? Excellent, good, normal, poor, or very poor? [Informant] My health is definitely normal, just peachy. I’m blind and deaf, and I have cancer to top it all off.”

Their assessment of the need for health care is often inaccurate. It is difficult, and sometimes impossible for an elderly person to assess or articulate their need for health care. Only acute pain prompts them to call a doctor. Constant ailments are perceived as normal. There is also an awkwardness associated with ongoing care seeking, which often turns out to be ineffective.

A man aged 91, Abakan

“We have a good doctor, she immediately prescribed Diclofenac and some ointments as well. She doesn’t even need to examine me, except perhaps to come by for the sake of formality. She could prescribe the medication over the phone because she remembers exactly what to prescribe.”

Interestingly, the oldest old do not tend to criticize doctors, as they see home visits or clinic appointments as a favor or a gift. Old people are useless – a common belief among the oldest old.

A daughter caring for her 90-year-old mother, Chernogorsk

“No one should be there for the salary they receive, but here they (doctors) are, sometimes even staying to talk to us and not leaving right away.”

On a separate note, it is necessary to discuss conducting interviews with the oldest old with serious cognitive impairments. Five respondents had serious disorders that prevented them from communicating with the interviewer. Although they are formally recognized as legally competent, all decisions are actually made for them by their relatives. Therefore, it is very difficult to obtain adequate information from the oldest old themselves. The only way to assess health and medical needs of someone with significant cognitive impairment is to talk to their caregivers.

Conclusion

This study analyzes the accessibility of health care for the oldest old (aged 85+) based on the findings of a qualitative sociological survey. In general, the results indicate that the current situation with care accessibility for the oldest old is extremely challenging. Often, the oldest

old cannot receive health care they need. The main factor contributing to low accessibility of medical services for this age group is physical barriers. Physical and cognitive limitations common in this age group, as well as general weakness, often prevent the oldest old from reaching health care facilities. Additionally, it is difficult for the oldest old to wait for a doctor's appointment at a health care facility. Physical barriers to accessing medical services are exacerbated by inadequate adaptation of medical buildings to accommodate the needs of the oldest age groups. Furthermore, the problem of physical access to medical services for the oldest old is aggravated by a significant shortage of doctors, especially narrow specialists, in health care facilities. Physical barriers to accessing medical services are most pronounced in the oldest old with limited mobility, bedridden, and those with significant cognitive impairments. Even the presence of a caregiver does not necessarily improve physical accessibility for the elderly.

Overall, this study conclusions confirm previous Russian studies' results, indicating strong barriers to physical access to health care for the oldest old with severe physical limitations and asthenia (e.g., Gruzdeva and Barsukov 2018; Mukharyamova and Savelyeva 2019; Trofimova et al. 2021). The oldest old are also the most vulnerable group in terms of physical accessibility of medical services in developed countries (European Commission 2008; Iecovich and Carmel 2009; Herr et al. 2014).

The study findings show that ageism, well-rooted in the Russian healthcare system, also prevents the oldest old from receiving medical services. Complaints from the oldest old are often ignored, ailments are attributed to the old age, and adequate modern treatment is not offered. Medical workers often fail to explain their conditions and treatments to the elderly patients, rushing and becoming irritated. Ageism towards the oldest old is also prevalent in the works by (Gruzdeva and Barsukov 2018; Trofimova et al. 2021). A review based on empirical experience in foreign countries confirms a more vulnerable position of the oldest age groups of the elderly (Ayalon and Tesch-Römer 2018).

There is also an issue with medication accessibility for the oldest old. Although the majority of the survey participants are eligible for subsidized prescription drugs, they are forced to purchase them at their own expense. The main reasons for refusing subsidized prescription drugs are limited physical accessibility of medical consultations and subsidized medications. Additionally, a significant limitation of drug therapy options for the oldest old is noncompliance with prescribed medication regimens, as well as independent selection of medications without a prescription. Such drug taking practices by the oldest old are often associated with limited accessibility of medical consultations. These results confirm previous literature conclusions about the oldest age groups being more likely not to comply with drug therapy protocols (Yap et al. 2016).

In developed countries, the oldest old face physical and sociocultural barriers to accessing medical services, as well as barriers to affordability (European Commission 2008; Palm et al. 2021). Our study failed to identify any cases when the oldest old refused medical services or medications due to the lack of funds. However, it is impossible to say that economic barriers do not exist for the oldest old seeking health care. It is possible that there is a bias: only those with sufficient funds use paid services or medicines, while others simply do not receive health care at all. Further research is needed to gain a deeper understanding of the economic barriers to care affordability for the oldest old. In any case, the prevalence of direct out-of-pocket payments among the oldest old is a cause of concern. WHO considers direct out-of-pocket payments to be the most unfair form of payment for medical services. These payments can lead to catastrophic expenses and significantly limit access to health care,

especially for the oldest old with high medical needs and relatively low incomes (Chubarova 2016).

Thus, the study findings indicate that health care is relatively inaccessible for the oldest old. Owing to the limited geography and scope of the qualitative study, the findings of this research must be carefully extrapolated to the entire population of the oldest old in Russia. It is important to note that accessibility of medical services for the oldest old may differ slightly across the Russian regions. Nevertheless, the study has identified barriers to accessing health care that are characteristic of this age group, and explored the mechanisms behind them. To obtain a more complete picture of the health characteristics and accessibility of health care for the oldest old in Russia, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive survey representing the population of this age group at the national and regional levels.

However, the study showed that the use of standard sociological tools in the group of the oldest old is difficult due to specific characteristics of their health, and may lead to the loss and/or distortion of information. In order to obtain adequate empirical information about the problems and needs of this population group, it is necessary to adapt the methodology of social research to the health characteristics of the oldest old and to conduct specialized surveys. Qualitative research methods can play an important role in obtaining information about the oldest old. These methods can be used as a tool for directly obtaining information about the health of the oldest old and as a tool for developing and refining specialized quantitative research methodologies.

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